

Data Management Plan (initial)

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Configuration Management

Nature of Deliverable		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
DATA	Datasets, microdata, etc	
DMP	Data management plan	
Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS projects.)	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Glossary

Acronym/abbreviations	
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DOI	Digital Objects Identifier
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
F.A.I.R. / FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IHI JU	Innovative Health Medicine Joint Undertaking
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OA	Open Access
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

One significant challenge in Research and Innovation projects is effective data management. This entails systematically collecting, storing, organizing, sharing, and maintaining data to enhance accessibility, performance, and timelines, as recommended by the FAIR principles.

The content presented in this document is part of PHARMECO's Work Package 1 (WP1), specifically Task 1.5 "Data Management," provided as deliverable D1.12. It summarizes the Data Management procedures to be followed during the project and the analysis conducted at Month 6 of the project.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is an essential project document that details how the PHARMECO consortium will organize data collection, storage, processing, and sharing during and after the project. In accordance with Horizon Europe's F.A.I.R. Data Management principles and the EU Commission's DMP template, it will be updated regularly to reflect significant changes such as new data regulations or updates in consortium policies on data sharing, de-identification, back-tracing, or anonymization.

Data will be generated from accessible information, project activities, trusted partners, external evaluators, and third-party beneficiaries addressing various use cases. This plan outlines a comprehensive strategy for data production and the management of project documentation.

When necessary, datasets will be anonymized. Personal data will comply with REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 and will only be available to authorized users through secure authentication.

This DMP is an evolving document which will be updated at least at the end of its third year and at the end of the project.

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1 Description of the deliverable's objective and the content

1.1 Purpose and scope

Projects such as PHARMECO are capable of generating extensive data, necessitating substantial exchange among project partners. The data typically originate from specific fields of study, encompassing laboratory tests, simulations, field research, and scientific observations.

PHARMECO collaborators will contribute valuable information through Open Access channels, including open datasets, open-source code, scientific publications, white papers, and anonymized survey results. It is crucial for consortium members to balance the open sharing of project-related information with the protection of sensitive data and compliance with GDPR regulations to avoid legal complications.

A Data Management Plan (DMP) serves as a guide for managing research data throughout the lifecycle of a project, from initiation to completion.

This DMP has three primary objectives:

- To describe the standards that ensure the proper generation, editing, redrafting, preservation, and distribution (for reuse or verification purposes) of various datasets;
- To outline the means and methods to determine, categorize (as public or classified), organize, curate, store, and disseminate the data to be created, processed, and amassed;
- To guarantee that these actions are aligned with current ethical and legal stipulations and, as much as possible, adaptable to future requirements.

This DMP is an evolving document which will be updated at least at the end of its third year and at the end of the project.

1.2 Data protection legislative framework

The PHARMECO consortium strictly follows Horizon Europe's standards and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. It complies with national and international laws, including Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on data protection and privacy directives. The consortium also adheres to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Convention 108, and Article 19 of Regulation No. 1291/2013/EC for ethical research principles.

1.3 Targeted audience

The targeted audience for this deliverable is:

- Beneficiaries, Associated Partners, Affiliated entities and Scientific Advisory Group in the PHARMECO project,
- European Commission,
- European and international stakeholders,
- Other Horizon Europe or sustainable chemistry related projects (clustering activities),
- Other relevant organizations (both public and private), including associations of relevant stakeholders.

1.4 Structure of the document

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2.1 provides the data summary.
- Section 2.2 presents the PHARMECO data re-usability process.
- Section 2.3 analyses the data sources.
- Section 2.4 discusses about the Data Management requirements and implementation.
- Section 2.5 discusses about the FAIR data principles.
- Section 2.6 covers the allocation of resources.
- Section 2.7 discusses on privacy and IPR.

2 Sections of the deliverables

2.1 Definitions

To generate knowledge, a project must rely on accurate data, as stated in the DIK triangle, used in knowledge management.

Figure 1 Knowledge Management, definitions and hierarchy.

Data consists of unstructured facts and figures without patterns or context. For data to become information, it must be contextualized, categorized, calculated and condensed. Knowledge uses the information implying know-how and understanding.

As all starts from the data, a Data Management Plan (DMP) is necessary to outline the data management lifecycle for generation or collection, processing, storage and sharing within a Horizon Europe project. To ensure research data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, a DMP must include detailed information about managing data **during and after the project**.

Key considerations include:

- the identification of the data types to be created, processed and/or generated,
- the owners of the respective procedures and the roles and groups of entities that will use the data,
- the identification of the methodologies and standards to be utilized,
- the metadata specifications that will ensure the data traceability and comprehensibility, clarifying measures in regard to access and sharing of the data, outlining the ways that the data will be conserved, including provision after the project's completion,
- the indications regarding the archiving and preservation of the project's open datasets.

A key part of the DMP is describing the type of Open Access (OA) available for the data. OA refers to providing online access to academic content at no cost to the user and allows for reuse. 'Scientific' includes all scholarly disciplines.

When applied to research and innovation, 'Scientific information' can refer to:

- Peer-reviewed academic research articles (published in academic journals), or

- Research data (data that underpins publications, managed data, and/or raw data).

Open Access to scientific publications denotes free online access for any potential reader/user.

The two main paths to OA include:

- Self-archiving or 'green' OA – the author or a proxy stores (deposits) the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication.
- OA publishing or 'gold' OA - an article is instantly published in an OA format. In this specific model, the cost of publication is transferred away from subscribing readers. The most typical business model involves one-time payments by the respective authors.

The OA mandate comprises two steps, a) depositing publications in repositories and b) providing OA to them.

Table 1 below focuses on clarifying a series of important fixed terms.

Table 1 Clarifications of terms

Metadata	Metadata is data used to describe other data. It summarizes basic information about data, which can make finding and working with instances of data easier.
Open access	Open access is defined as the principle that research information must be accessible to relevant users, on equal terms, and at the lowest possible cost. Access must be easy, user-friendly and, if possible, internet-based.
Open research data	Openly accessible research data can typically be managed (i.e., to be accessed, and/or exploited and/or reproduced and/or disseminated), free of charge.
Research data	Research data is essential for generating research results. This data is collected, observed, or acquired from various sources and analyzed to produce new research findings. These findings form the basis of research papers that are submitted for publication in academic channels.
Research data repositories	Research data repositories are defined as online archives (digital data storage platforms) for preserving (and sharing) research data. Such information can be subject based and/or thematic, institutional or centralised.
Secondary data	Secondary data are data that already exist, because of some primary gathering or processing (metadata), which was conducted regardless of the research to be conducted.

2.2 Data summary

Adhering to the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe, a Data Management Plan (DMP) is essential for ensuring efficient data handling. Therefore, it is vital to outline the types of data anticipated to be generated throughout the project:

1. Data derived from readily available sources or other subjects relevant to the project's objectives.
2. Data resulting from activities carried out by project partners, including technical data processing,
3. Data created involving third-party(ies), such as those created by other projects or initiatives.

2.2.1 State of Purpose of the Data Collection / Generation

The PHARMECO project will accumulate data from a variety of sources, which include project partners, stakeholders, and various other external contributors. The related data activities such as the collection, the storage, and the processing of information submitted by all project applicants is considered crucial.

The data, in all formats, will be utilized for three primary objectives:

- To assess deliverables and proposals,
- To evaluate impact, and
- To conduct meaningful (academic and business) research.

2.2.2 Types and Formats of Data Generated / Collected

Research data is information like facts or figures collected for analysis and reasoning. It can include statistics, experiment results, measurements, fieldwork observations, survey results, interview recordings, and images. The focus is on digital research data that users can access, mine, use, reproduce, and share freely without charge.

Table 2 Examples of types of research data collected/generated during PHARMECO application preparation

Data Type	Format	Size	Openness
Raw data from instruments, like HPLC, MS, NMR, etc	Proprietary formats specific to the manufacturer of the instrument	<10MB/datafile	Decided on case-by-case basis, taking into account (i) IP and (ii) balancing the benefits of openness with practical considerations like costs and resources.
Processed experimental data, analyzed exp. data (graphs, tables etc)	csv, xlsx, docx, pptx, png, jpeg, svg, tiff, pdf etc	<10MB/datafile	Accessible after IP protection (if relevant), for example as supplementary data together with scientific papers
Datasets (eg energy/mass inputs/outputs, process opt. data, PAT data)	Txt, csv, xlsx, json, xml etc	from 1MB up to GB/dataset	OPEN, unless (i) commercially sensitive information, (ii) confidential information
Databases (infrastructure, raw materials, LCI etc)	MySQL, MongoDB, Ecolnvent format	Up to GB/database	OPEN, unless (i) commercially sensitive information, (ii) confidential information
Models (flow sheet models, chemometric models, AI-driven predictive models etc)	.bkp, vsdx, .vsd, .mdl etc	<10MB	Accessible after IP protection (if relevant)
Algorithms/code (tools for route design, prospective sustain. assessment etc)	.py, .txt, .R	<10MB	Accessible after IP protection (if relevant)

A first iteration of identification of datasets was conducted among the Work Packages during the period January to March 2025, that led to the Table 2 presenting the PHARMECO datasets initial overview, focusing on the data types, origin, format and respective work package for the expected data.

Table 3 PHARMECO datasets initial overview

Data description	Data type	Data volume	Data origin	Data sharing
Work Package 1 - Coordination, management and governance				
General Documentation and reporting	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP1 based on partners contributions	Internal SharePoint Funding and Tenders Portal
Financial and effort data	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP1 based on partners data	Internal SharePoint and Funding and Tenders Portal
Governing Bodies and consortium composition	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP1 based on governing bodies composition	Internal SharePoint
Meeting slidedecks and meeting minutes	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP1 based on governing bodies composition	Internal SharePoint
Action logs, decision logs, risk logs, KPI logs	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP1 based on governing bodies composition	Internal SharePoint
Work Package 2 - Route design according to SSbD methodology and using "SELECT"				
General Documentation and reporting	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP2 based on partners contributions	By default, documentation and reporting will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Documentation and reporting

				subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Processed data and generated by modeling (graphs, tables, input from surveys)	csv, xlsx, docx, tiff, png, pptx, jpeg, etc	<1Gb	Created by WP2 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets retrieved from databases (e.g. input/outputs, ecotoxicity characteristics)	csv, xlsx, ecospold, pdf,...	< 2Gb	Databases (e.g. ecoinvent, Scifinder, etc.)	By default, the datasets will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Datasets subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Mapped data from other tasks, educational material	Docx,pptx,xlsx,pdf, jpeg	<1Gb	Collected from partners in	By default, the data will be stored on the internal

			WP2, WP7, WP8	SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets from experimental data (e.g. energy/mass inputs/outputs, process opt. data)	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<1Gb	Collected from partners contribution, created by WP3,4,5,6,7	By default, data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets from industry partners (for sustainability assessments/model training data, e.g. energy/mass balances, inputs/outputs for LCA/circularity/criticality, economic data, chemical reaction schemes, green chemistry indicators)	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, rdf, svg, etc	<5 Gb	Collected from industry partners contribution, created by WP2	Local server of LU, with restricted access to people working on PHARMECO
Models (AI-driven prediction model)	Py, mat, csv, rdf, svg, etc.		Created by WP2 based on partners contributions	Internal SharePoint until IP protection (if relevant) and/or publication

Digital decision support tool	Pdf, xlsx, html, js, css, mat, py etc.		Created by WP2 based on partners contributions	Internal SharePoint until IP protection (if relevant) and/or publication
Conceptual framework (integrated assessment)	Pdf, pptx, etc.	<1Gb	Created by WP2 based on literature, stakeholders input, modelling	Internal SharePoint until IP protection (if relevant) and/or publication
Work Package 3 - Chemical synthesis platforms				
General Documentation and reporting	docx, pptx, xlsx, pdf	<1Gb	Created by WP3 based on partners contributions	By default, documentation and reporting will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Documentation and reporting subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Data extracted from databases (references for reaction and process parameters, analytical references, etc.)	txt, docx, xlsx, pdf, etc.	<1Gb	Created by WP3 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be

				made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets (process parameters, process opt. data, reaction conditions, experimental procedures and protocols, etc.)	docx, xlsx, pdf, etc.	<5Gb	Created by / collected from WP3 partners	By default, the datasets will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Processed experimental data, analyzed exp. data (graphs, tables, etc.)	xlsx, docx, pptx, png, jpeg, tiff, pdf, etc.	<5Gb	Created by WP3 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Raw data from measurements	txt, csv, tiff, jpg, png, equipment specific formats, etc.	<10Gb	Created by WP3 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will

				not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Work Package 4 - Biomanufacturing				
General Documentation and reporting	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP4 based on partners contributions	By default, documentation and reporting will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Documentation and reporting subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Raw data from measurements	ASCII, txt, csv, tiff, .lsx, proprietary formats for used equipment, etc.	<5Gb	Created by WP4 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets (eg energy/mass inputs/outputs for LCA, process opt. data, PAT data)	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<10Gb	Created by / collected from WP4 partners	By default, the datasets will be stored on the internal

				<p>SharePoint until publication.</p> <p>Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.</p>
<p>Datasets (process parameters, process opt. data, reaction conditions, experimental procedures and protocols, etc.)</p>	docx, xlsx, pdf, etc.	<5Gb	Created by / collected from WP4 partners	<p>By default, the datasets will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication.</p> <p>Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.</p>
<p>Data generated by modelling or extracted from databases</p>	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<5Gb	Created by WP4 based on partners contributions	<p>By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication.</p> <p>Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.</p>

Processed experimental data , analyzed exp. data (graphs, tables etc)	csv, xlsx, docx, pptx, png, jpeg, svg, tiff, pdf etc	<1Gb	Created by WP4 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Models (AI-driven prediction model)	Py, mat, csv etc.	<1Gb	Created by WP4 based on partners contributions	Internal sharepoint until IP protection and/or publication
Work Package 5 - Decontamination				
General Documentation and reporting	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP5 based on partners contributions	By default, documentation and reporting will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Documentation and reporting subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Data generated by modelling or extracted from databases	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<5Gb	Created by WP5 based on partners contributions	Sensitive, except for Task 5.1.4

Datasets (eg energy/mass inputs/outputs for LCA, process opt. data, PAT data)	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<1Gb	Created by / collected from WP5 partners	By default, the datasets will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Processed experimental data , analyzed exp. data (graphs, tables etc)	csv, xlsx, docx, pptx, png, jpeg, svg, tiff, pdf etc	<1Gb	Created by WP5 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Raw data from measurements	ASCII, txt, csv, tiff, .lsx, proprietary formats for used equipment, etc.	<5Gb	Created by WP5 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be

				made on a case-by-case basis.
Work Package 6 - Pilot manufacturing, process design, Pilot platform				
General Documentation and reporting	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP6 based on partners contributions	By default, documentation and reporting will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Documentation and reporting subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis..
Data generated by modelling	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<5Gb	Created by WP6 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets (eg energy/mass inputs/outputs for LCA, process opt. data, PAT data)	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<1Gb	Created by / collected from WP6 partners	By default, the datasets will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication.

				Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Processed experimental data , analyzed exp. data (graphs, tables etc)	csv, xlsx, docx, pptx, png, jpeg, svg, tiff, pdf etc	<1Gb	Created by WP6 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Raw data from measurements	ASCII, txt, csv, tiff, .lsx, proprietary formats for used equipment, etc.	<5Gb	Created by WP6 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Work Package 7				
General Documentation and reporting	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP7 based on	By default, documentation and reporting will

			partners contributions	be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Documentation and reporting subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Processed data and generated by modeling (graphs, tables, input from surveys)	csv, xlsx, docx, tiff, png, pptx, jpeg, etc	<1Gb	Created by WP7 based on partners contributions	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets retrieved from databases (e.g. input/outputs, ecotoxicity characteristics)	csv, xlsx, ecospold, pdf,...	< 2Gb	Databases (e.g. ecoinvent, PREMIER)	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be

				made on a case-by-case basis.
Mapped data from other tasks, educational material	Docx,pptx,xlsx,pdf, jpeg	<1Gb	Collected from partners in WP2, WP7, WP8	By default, the data will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets from experimental data (e.g. energy/mass inputs/outputs, process opt. data)	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<1Gb	Collected from partners contribution, created by WP3,4,5,6,7	By default, the datasets will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Datasets from industry partners (for sustainability assessments/model training data, e.g. energy/mass balances, inputs/outputs for LCA/circularity/criticality, socio-economic data, chemical reaction schemes, green chemistry indicators)	Txt, doc, csv, xlsx, json, xml pdf, etc	<5 Gb	Collected from industry partners contribution, created by WP7	Local server of UGENT, with restricted access to people working on PHARMECO
Models (AI-driven prediction model)	Py, mat, csv etc.		Created by WP7 based on	Internal sharepoint until IP

			partners contributions	protection and/or publication
Digital decision support tool	Pdf, xlsx, html, js, css, mat, py etc.		Created by WP7 based on partners contributions	Internal sharepoint until IP protection and/or publication
Conceptual framework (integrated assessment)	Pdf, pptx, etc.	<1Gb	Created by WP7 based on literature, stakeholders input, modelling	Internal sharepoint until IP protection and/or publication
Work Package 8 - Standardization and harmonization of sustainability assessment systems				
General Documentation and reporting	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP8 based on partners contributions	Internal SharePoint until publication
Meeting slidedecks and meeting minutes	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	< 1Gb	Created by WP8 based on partners contributions	Internal SharePoint
Mapped data from other tasks, educational material	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	<1Gb	Collected from partners in WP7	Internal Sharepoint until publication
Work Package 9 - Dissemination, exploitation, communication and networking activities				
General documentation (corporate slide deck, project information etc)	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	<1Gb	Created by WP9 based on partners contributions	PHARMECO website, LinkedIn
Data collected at workshops or from interactions with experts	.docx, .pptx, .xlsx, .pdf	<GB	Collected from workshop participants or other stakeholders	By default, the datasets will be stored on the internal SharePoint until publication. Data subject to publication restrictions, as outlined in the consortium agreement, will

					not be published; decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis.
Publications (abstract, papers, presentations, etc)	(abstract, conferences)	.pdf	<1Gb	Created by Partners	Zenodo, open access sites

2.2.3 Data Quality Assurance Process

The data quality principle requires all information to be accurate and up-to-date. Personal data processing will comply with EU, national, and international laws, following these outlined "data quality" principles:

- Processing of data should be sufficient, pertinent, and not superfluous.
- Data must be precise and continually updated.
- Data should be processed in a fair and lawful manner.
- Data should be processed respecting the rights of the data subjects.
- Processing of data should be performed securely.
- Data should be retained only as long as necessary for the sole purpose of the project as defined in the Description of Action. The data quality assurance process will be led in accordance with the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons about the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

2.2.4 Dataset template

In order to ensure proper identification and traceability of data used in the context of PHARMECO implementation, a dataset fact sheet is designed (Table 4) and will be used within all Work Packages.

Table 4 PHARMECO dataset fact sheet template

DATA SUMMARY	
Dataset reference	Dataset number/name
Reference Work Package / Deliverable	WPX DX.X
Data Manager	Referring person/s and organizations who takes responsibility of this dataset
Date of update of the dataset table	Date
Specific Metadata	Keyword(s) that characterize data to make it linked/searchable
Description and purpose	Data description and purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project.
Data origin	Internal research / Existing Knowledge / Literature / Interviews / Monitoring
Data Size	Preliminary estimation of the expected size of the dataset
Availability	Open access / Restricted to the consortium / Confidential
Accessibility	How is the data be made accessible (e.g., Authentication with

DATA SUMMARY	
	username and password, by deposition in a repository)? How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? Indicate the existence of embargo period if any.
Standards	Reference to existing standards in topic area governing data collection, aggregation, storage and sharing. Adaptation of dataset to community standards to maximize interoperability with other researchers. Potential license restrictions. Discoverability. Need for aggregation and anonymization. For example : General adherence to GDPR ruling and to the project consortium signed agreement (CA).
PID (Persistent Identifier of the dataset) or identification of the storage repository	Link to the PID if applicable Link to the storage repository (even if internal repository)
Does the data underpin a publication	Yes / No / Planned
PID (Persistent Identifier of the publication)	Link to the PID if applicable
Is the meta data accessible through open access?	Yes / No It might be necessary for contacts purpose if the data is confidential (an NDA could be signed if necessary for those willing to access it)
Data format	E.g., docx, pdf, xls, csv, etc.
Software tool	What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?
Utility & Re-use	Clarify to whom the data might be useful: partners in other tasks / WPs; third parties in the future (e.g., researchers, institutions, organizations, etc.).
Archiving and preservation (storage/backup)	Procedure for long-term preservation, length of preservation, an estimation of costs and how this will be covered.
Ethical aspects	Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

2.3 Data re-usability

Non confidential data will be promptly disclosed and posted on the partners' trusted repositories and if possible on the research data online repository (Zenodo PHARMECO community).

2.3.1 Re-use of existing data

The project involves the utilization or integration of previously amassed research or personal data. The user will check under which terms and conditions the data is shared. In case there is a licence, the user has to assess that the licence gives the permission to use them. A second aspect will be to check whether there is sufficient metadata to enable data reuse.

2.3.2 Increasing data re-use through clarifying licences

2.3.2.1 Open Science & Open Access to Scientific Publications

Project beneficiaries are obligated to provide open access to peer-reviewed scientific papers linked to their results. This specifically involves ensuring that:

- A machine-readable digital version of the published work or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a reliable scientific publication repository no later than the publication date.
- The publication deposited in the repository is immediately available with open access, under the most recent version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a license offering similar rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial use and derivative works (such as CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND).
- Any information regarding research outputs or any other tools and instruments required to verify the scientific publication's conclusions is provided via the repository.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must maintain enough intellectual property rights to fulfil the open access requirements.

The metadata of the deposited publications must be made open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or an equivalent, conforming to the FAIR principles (especially being machine-actionable), and must provide at minimum, information about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym, and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant. If applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output, or any other tools and instruments required to validate the publication's conclusions.

Only full open publication fees are applicable.

2.3.2.2 Open Science & Research Data Management

As soon as feasibly possible and within the deadlines outlined in the DMP, the data must be deposited in a trusted repository. Beneficiaries are also expected to facilitate open access, via the repository, to the deposited data as soon as possible. This is to be achieved under the most recent version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or an equivalent license, while adhering to the principle of 'as open as possible as closed as necessary'.

However, open access to some or all data might not be provided if it conflicts with the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including commercial exploitation, EU competitive interests, or any obligations under the Grant Agreement (GA) or the Consortium Agreement. Any such instances must be justified in the next versions of the DMP.

Information regarding any research output or other tools required to reuse or validate the data should also be provided via the repository.

Furthermore, metadata of the deposited data must be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, while safeguarding legitimate interests or constraints and aligning with the FAIR principles, particularly being machine-actionable.

The metadata should provide information about datasets, Horizon Europe funding, grant project name, acronym, and grant agreement number, licensing terms, and persistent identifiers for the dataset, authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant.

When applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

2.3.3 Data re-usability time-length

The Consortium is committed to keeping the data usable for as long as feasible following the project's completion. **An initial duration of five (5) years** has been set; nonetheless, this period could be extended with the agreement of the partners.

2.4 Data sources and acquisition

The data that will be gathered in the frame of the PHARMECO project comprise both publicly accessible data and internal (operational data), which are mostly generated and collected by the partner entities. For datasets already identified (Table 3), the source is already qualified.

The main data sources for the PHARMECO project include:

- Data being sourced from various documents, such as publications, and
- Operational data created during the execution of the project.

2.5 Data management requirements

In the PHARMECO project, data management is a strategic approach for handling all generated or collected outcomes during its duration. This includes data categorization, storage, performance, protection and security, compliance with FAIR principles, and data ethics.

2.5.1 Data classification

For proper data handling, datasets must be initially segmented into public and non-public categories. The classification of these diverse datasets can be done by addressing the following queries:

1. Does an outcome deliver considerable value to others or is it required to comprehend a scientific conclusion?

A positive answer to this query classifies the result as public (qualified for open access). A negative response categorizes the result as non-public.

2. Does an outcome encompass personal data that goes beyond the author's name?

An affirmative answer to this question classifies the result as non-public. Personal data, excluding the name, must be expunged if it is to be published.

3. Can an outcome enable the recognition of individuals even in the absence of their names?

Datasets will be anonymized for research and impact assessment purposes. The collection of personal data within the project will be minimal and will require the informed consent of participants regarding the use of their personal data. A positive answer to this question classifies the result as non-public.

4. Can an outcome be misused for a purpose that is generally undesirable to society or contravenes societal norms and the project's ethics?

A positive answer to this question classifies the result as non-public.

5. Does an outcome involve one or more project partners' business or trade secrets?

An affirmative answer to this question classifies the result as non-public. Any business or trade secrets must be excised in line with all partners' stipulations before it can be published.

6. Does an outcome mention technology that is part of an ongoing, project-related patent application?

An affirmative answer to this query classifies the result as non-public. Naturally, results may be published once the patent application is submitted.

7. Does an outcome compromise any project partner's security interests?

A positive answer to this question classifies the result as non-public.

2.5.2 Data protection and security

Processing of personal data will follow the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and until valid, the repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR).

As a result of the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), stipulated in Article 35 (1) of the GDPR, necessary organisational and technical strategies will be deployed to ensure the security of personal data. This includes methods such as anonymisation, pseudonymisation, encryption during storage and transmission, hashing, tokenization, and the use of key management practices to protect data across all applications and platforms. The personal data collected as part of the project will be strictly confined to the project's objectives, and participants' informed consent for data use will be mandatory.

Operational data that is internally gathered or produced by partners during the entire project duration will be stored in data repositories located on each partner's individual servers. These servers will be securely housed in locked rooms, with stringent access controls in compliance with relevant security standards, and they will employ cutting-edge security measures.

Repository access will be exclusively provided to authorized individuals at both the physical and network levels. If datasets are contained within databases, only authorized users with unique usernames and passwords can gain access, adhering to the rules of access privileges.

The transfer of data will adhere to established best practices, which include encrypting files and securely transmitting the corresponding keys or passwords.

In the case of already identified personal data (names and email addresses of PHARMECO participants), the data is only accessible to people registered in the PHARMECO SharePoint, which access is granted with a double authentication system.

2.5.3 Data management implementation

This section provides an overview of the specific provisions, foreseen for the management of each project dataset and databases (DBs) in table form.

Table 5 PHARMECO data management implementation

Dataset	Classification	Archiving	Safety & Security	FAIR	Privacy & Data protection
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Project public documentation	Public	PHARMECO website Zenodo	N/A	Appropriate metadata	N/A
Scientific publications	Public	OA websites (publishers, via DOI), PHARMECO website, Zenodo	N/A	Appropriate metadata	N/A
Operational public data	Public	PHARMECO website Zenodo	N/A	Appropriate metadata	Potential anonymisation
Operational private data	Confidential	Partners' repositories	Policies of beneficiaries	Partners policies	Partners policies

2.6 Fair data principles

The FAIR data principles aimed at swiftly disseminating the data outcomes of a research project are presented in Table 6 that follows.

Table 6 Data management according to fair principles data source and acquisition

FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES	
Data should be Findable	<p>F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.</p> <p>F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below).</p> <p>F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.</p> <p>F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.</p>
Data should be Accessible	<p>A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol.</p> <p>A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.</p> <p>A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.</p> <p>A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.</p>
Data should be Interoperable	<p>I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p> <p>I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies and definitions that follow FAIR principles.</p> <p>I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.</p>

<p>Data should be Reusable</p>	<p>R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.</p> <p>R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.</p> <p>R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.</p> <p>R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.</p>
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2.6.1 Making data findable

All data management actions, like storage, processing, and mutual sharing of information among project participants will be facilitated via a dedicated platform, SharePoint, provided by Benkei, while the broader public engagement with the project's findings will be enabled and broadcasted through the official project website and the Zenodo community.

In addition, all data will be archived on each beneficiary repositories for a minimum duration of five (5) years post- project completion.

The adopted naming convention will succinctly detail the content, the data-collecting institution, and the month of publication. Version control will be invoked in instances where a participant wishes to withdraw their data; here, a version number will be incorporated into the file name.

The necessary technical steps will be implemented to ensure that data does not reveal the identities of individuals involved, and as such, identifiable data that lead to real names will not be distributed.

2.6.1.1 Discoverability of the Data

Data generated within the scope of PHARMECO will be rendered traceable and locatable via unique identification protocols. All files will be distinctly identified through the utilization of standardized naming conventions and file versioning procedures. Moreover, any research data generated will be accompanied by metadata annotations, adhering to certain standards like the Dublin Core generic metadata standard, with the aim of describing a broad spectrum.

To ensure that PHARMECO paves a path in alignment with the FAIR data principles, (meta)data will:

- Be associated with a unique and permanent global identifier
- Include comprehensive metadata for complete data interpretation, and
- Be catalogued in a source which serves and honours easy searching.

2.6.1.2 Data Identification Mechanisms

All documents will carry the project's name, along with a unique, enduring designator for the document type and number. The version of the document will be incorporated both into its name and its title.

PHARMECO will disseminate data through academic articles as well, in such instances, Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) will be issued by the publisher.

For other forms of written work, like reports and policy recommendations, DOIs will be allocated via the repository where they are archived (for instance, Zenodo).

2.6.1.3 Naming Conventions

In order to (i) bolster the searchability and discoverability of data, and (ii) offer insights into the content, status, and versioning of files, every produced dataset (such as datasets, deliverables, etc.) will adhere to a consistent naming protocol and will incorporate a table for version control.

The guidelines for naming project documents will be:

- select identifier names that are succinct yet meaningful,
- avoid using acronyms that are not universally recognized,
- refrain from using abbreviations or shortened forms,
- steer clear of characters that are language-specific or non-alphanumeric,
- append a two-digit numerical suffix to distinguish new versions of a document, and
- include dates in reverse order, using four digits for the year: YYYYMMDD.

Examples:

- For deliverables: Project's name - Dx.y - [Name of the deliverable owner as described in the DoA].
- For datasets: Project's name - WP [Work Package number] - T [Task number; description of the activity] - Name.

PHARMECO partners will employ user-friendly search keywords to promote the effective reuse of data by all stakeholders. The metadata standards that PHARMECO adopts offer the ability to annotate both the data gathered/generated and its substance with keywords.

Typically, the keywords will encompass terms linked to the relevant subject matters, such as Route design, Decontamination, Pilot and scale up, Cradle-to-grave, LCA, Harmonized standards, Pharmaceutical Manufacturing, Continuous manufacturing, Process intensification, digital twin, etc.

Additionally, project-specific keywords, like PHARMECO, Horizon Europe, IHI JU, Partners' name etc., will also be used.

The selected keywords will accurately mirror the content of the datasets and will avoid terms that only appear once or twice within them.

2.6.2 Open-data accessibility

Subject to ethical considerations and participant consent, data will be as much accessible as possible.

Different levels of dissemination will be applicable to PHARMECO reports and documentation.

- Public reports will be disseminated via public platforms, whereas confidential reports will only be shared within the consortium.
- Scientific publications will be freely accessible and will be uploaded to public repositories.
- Partners will exchange data through a shared space, based on SharePoint.

2.6.3 Data interoperability

The principle of interoperability demands data to be machine-readable and the terminology to be consistent. In adherence to the principle of Data Interoperability, PHARMECO partners will ensure seamless data interoperability across different systems.

2.6.3.1 Interoperability of Data Assessment

Partners will be responsible for storing the data in a comprehensive format and adapted to the real and current needs of the possible practitioners interested in using, merging or exploiting the data generated throughout the project.

2.6.3.2 Interdisciplinarity and Transdisciplinarity

PHARMECO aims to foster knowledge co-creation among individuals from diverse fields, transcending traditional disciplinary boundaries. The project inherently embraces an interdisciplinary approach, as it brings together expertise from various scientific domains.

2.6.4 Data archiving

2.6.4.1 PHARMECO website

The consortium will establish a dedicated website for the project. The webpage's design and development are undertaken by consortium partner Benkei. www.pharmeco.eu is today a landing page that will soon be enriched with the project's goals, overall methodology, participating partners, and progression status. A "News and Events" section will offer regular updates, and a specified area for publications allows for the download of public deliverables, reports, and white papers.

To ensure wide-reaching dissemination of the project outcomes, Benkei employs digital marketing strategies that include content for social media platforms like LinkedIn, press releases, interviews, videos, and infographics.

All documents will be uploaded in the universally accessible portable document format (PDF). Every download is supplemented with basic metadata, such as the document's title and type.

2.6.4.2 SharePoint

SharePoint is a suite of web applications created by Microsoft, offering a collaborative portal combining collaboration tools such as electronic document management and a search engine.

Benkei is providing access to a dedicated PHARMECO SharePoint space and ensures internal maintenance and backup. SharePoint will be utilized for the project's internal storage of project-associated data. Access to the PHARMECO SharePoint is exclusively managed by Benkei and only authorized PHARMECO partners are granted access. The SharePoint will be accessible up to 2 years after the end of the project: during this period, all partners will be invited to autonomously download and store on their own archive repository the PHARMECO data.

2.6.4.3 ZENODO

Zenodo is a research data archive/ online repository which helps researchers to share research results and project documentation in a wide variety of formats. It was created through EC's OpenAIRE+ project and is now hosted at CERN using one of Europe's most reliable hardware infrastructures. Data are backed nightly and replicated to different locations. Zenodo supports not only the publication of scientific papers or public documentation, but also the publication of any structured research data (e.g., using XML).

The property rights or ownership of a result does not change by uploading it to Zenodo.

All public results related to scientific publications that will be produced during the PHARMECO project will be uploaded to Zenodo for long-term storage and open access.

2.7 Allocation of resources

Benkei bears the responsibility for maintaining the project document repository. Each partner, on the other hand, is accountable for the recoverability of the data they generate.

After the project concludes, no additional funding will be needed for data storage and maintenance costs.

2.8 Data protection and security

2.8.1 Privacy and data protection

Datasets will be anonymized for research and impact assessment purposes. The collection of personal data within the project, if needed, will be confined to project participants, and participants' informed consent for the usage of their personal data will be necessary.

2.8.2 Intellectual property rights (IPR) guidelines

In the PHARMECO project, managing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) is crucial for maximizing results and protecting intellectual property. Identifying IPR for datasets, software, tools, and knowledge is essential, which involves understanding licensing, usage terms, and access rights.

IPR management is handled within the project, covering IPR administration at the Consortium level. This includes managing background access, ownership of new results and innovations, access rights, and IPR protection during dissemination activities.

The activities of Work Package 9 - Dissemination, exploitation, communication and networking activities, jointly led by Novo Nordisk and RISE, and more specifically “Task 9.3 - Management of KERs, exploitation strategy & IPR protection”, led by UCB Be, will provide details of IPR and ownership of results to safeguard the rights of all partners.

Specifically, the associated deliverables will detail the ownership of background and foreground intellectual property. They will also explain how IPR will be protected after the project's completion and the ownership rights of any results generated post-grant period.

Moreover, the duties, rights, and responsibilities of the partners are detailed in the Consortium Agreement (CA) signed by all parties. Matters related to intellectual property rights (IPR), including joint ownership of results and situations where IPR is impacted, are also outlined in the CA. Additionally, the background contributions each partner provides to the project are specified in the CA.

2.8.3 Managing Open-Source Licenses

Although the consortium supports open-source principles, some data cannot be shared due to proprietary constraints. They will use a layered approach: Solutions will be copyrighted with licenses that respect company terms; open-source data will be released under suitable licenses like CC-BY. All software licenses for algorithms, components, and modules will be reviewed to determine the appropriate licensing.

3 Conclusion

This document outlines the data management plan for the PHARMECO project and provides an initial examination of the data sources that will be utilized or created throughout the project, as identified by the consortium partners. It also details how the project results will be disseminated.

By project results, this deliverable includes various types of information such as scientific publications, white papers, open-source code, open datasets, used or created by different entities involved in the project.

The report's current version contains research data related to the project's work packages, managed based on their availability (public or sensitive/confidential).

Moreover, the PHARMECO Data Management adheres to the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe, meaning that the data must be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

This report will be a continuously updated document throughout the project. The Data Management Plan (DMP) will be revised whenever significant changes occur, such as new data, innovations, patent filings, changes in consortium members, and more. Two official updates, planned respectively at Month 36 (October 27) and Month 72 (October 30) are already included in the deliverables' plan.